

#WeNeedLocalFood

Key guidelines and sample materials
for use in social media

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#WeNeedLocalFood Tool

This document presents a set of **materials, communication guidelines, social media messages and resources** that brand owners can use to engage producers and consumers in order to identify needs and demands.

The content includes:

- Key social media channels
- Best practices to share your content
- Key facts and messages about the Short Food Supply Chain
- Sample key words and images for social media
- Related accounts
- References

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Key Social Media Channels

Social media are interactive technologies that allow the creation or sharing and/or exchange of information, ideas, interests, and other forms of expression via virtual communities and networks. Below are the most popular social media channels across Europe and some key facts for each:

- 2 Billion users
- 47% over the age of 35
- Good for Business to Consumers (B2C) with targeted audience

- 675 million users
- 61% between 30 and 64
- Professional relationships, aimed at Business-to-Business (B2B) companies

- 2 billion users
- 59% between 18 and 29
- Great for Business to Consumers (B2C) with visual based products or services

- 330 million users
- 35% between 18 and 29
- Popular among celebrities, politicians, journalists and news outlets

Social Media Best Practices: Facebook

CONTENT

- No character limits
- Media Attachment:
 - Photos
 - Videos
 - Links

APPROACH

An informal social media channel to post news and make announcements that can reach a wide audience. Multimedia content is often more attractive.

TIPS

- Engage with groups to increase views on your company profile
- Use visual elements: Pictures, GIFs, audiovisual
- Use clear and friendly tone

Social Media Best Practices: LinkedIn

CONTENT

- No character limits
- Media Attachment:
 - Photos
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Social Media Best Practices: Instagram

CONTENT

- Mainly images
- Short text
- Videos
- Livestream

APPROACH

An informal social network, mainly used to post pictures. It is useful for promoting visual products / services if your target is among the younger generations.

TIPS

- Engage with other accounts by tagging @ them
- Set up Some guidelines in order to harmonise the look and feel

Social Media Best Practices: Twitter/X

CONTENT

Text up to 280 characters + media attachments and quoted tweets (displaying someone else's tweet within your own).

APPROACH

To share short comments, make announcements that can instantaneously reach a large audience or retweet relevant contents - ideal for live communication during events.

TIPS

- Use hashtags # and mentions @ to tag appropriate handles.
- Use visual elements: pictures, videos and GIFs.
- Keep your posts short, clear and catchy.
- Create Twitter lists to categorize your account into themes.

TOP 10 KEY MESSAGES ABOUT SHORT FOOD SUPPLY CHAIN (SFSC)

- 1.** SFSC advantages include a **fairer price for farmers, access to fresh and seasonal produce for consumers, a reduced environmental impact and greater social cohesion at local level.**²
- 2.** Consumers associate **local products with higher quality standards** (freshness, nutritional value), **healthy eating, environmentally friendly production methods** and a **lower carbon footprint.**²
- 3.** According to the 2011 Eurobarometer survey, **9/10 citizens agree that there are benefits to buying products from a local farm.**²
- 4.** SFSCs are a way to **reconnect producers and consumers** and to **re-localise agricultural production.**²
- 5.** Products sold in local food systems are generally produced in a more **environmentally sustainable** way, using **less inputs such as pesticides, synthetic fertilisers, animal feed, water and energy.**²

TOP 10 KEY MESSAGES ABOUT SHORT FOOD SUPPLY CHAIN (SFSC)

6. SFSC products require **less packaging** than supermarket products and **less energy** for storage, as they are **fresh and seasonal**.²
7. SFSCs also contribute to social **cohesion in urban areas**, by reconnecting the population to the place of food production and by providing **fresh and quality products at affordable prices**.²
8. Many SFSCs are characterised by full or partial **organic farming methods**.²
9. SFSCs require **less transport** which means **energy savings** and reduced **environmental impact**.²
10. SFSCs can be understood as supply chains related to ‘**sales in proximity**’ in the sense that locally grown or produced foods are served to local consumers, where the number of intermediaries is minimised, the ideal being a **direct contact between the producer and the consumer**.

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Hashtags are commonly used on microblogging and photo-sharing services. They can be used in any of the following platforms: Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, LinkedIn.

By using #WeNeedLocalFood:

PRODUCERS can learn in real time the needs from consumers

CONSUMERS can post their needs and/or interact with SFSC businesses

Other hashtags can be used for a better social media positioning. The following hashtags have been pulled from [best-hashtags.com](https://www.best-hashtags.com):

#agrifood #agriculture #agritech #farm #agrifoodEU #farming #natural #sustainable #bioeconomy #ecological #eco #quality #organic #sustainability #farmers #consumers #ShortFoodSupplyChain #SFSC #naturefood #vegan #healthyfood #organicfood #vegetarian #plantbased #bio #ecofriendly

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Below are some examples of social media publications on **Facebook!**

🗣️ Have you considered the following reasons why #WeNeedLocalFood?

📄 According to the Eurobarometer survey, consumers associate local products with higher quality standards such as freshness and nutritional value, among other benefits.

🍷🍅 Indeed, the products coming from #ShortFoodSupplyChain business models are characterised by full or partial organic farming methods where you can have direct contact with the producer.

→ Find us here: Add your Website / Location

💡 Did you know that you can contact us through the hashtag #WeNeedLocalFood?

🗣️🗣️ Through this hashtag we can learn from you your real time needs as well as interact with local producers and know more about the benefits of our business based on #ShortFoodSupplyChain

📱 We invite you to interact with us and be part of our community! 😊

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Below are some examples of social media publications on **Twitter!**

📝 Know some of the reasons why #WeNeedLocalFood:

- 🍎 We need high quality products
- 🤝 We need to reconnect producers and consumers
- 🍷 We need fresh and seasonal products
- ♻️ We need environmentally sustainable products

📌 These are just a few examples why #WeNeedLocalFood!

Stay tuned for upcoming information!

🗣️🗣️ Did you know that by using the hashtag #WeNeedLocalFood, you can interact with local producers so that they can learn your real-time needs while you learn more about the benefits of our business based on #ShortFoodSupplyChains?

📱 We invite you to interact with us and be part of our community

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Below are some examples of social media publications on **LinkedIn!**

🔗 Do you know the benefits of the #ShortFoodSupplyChain products?

♻️ Less packaging!

📦 Less energy for storage

🚚 Less transport

👨‍🍳 Fresh and quality products

...and much more #WeNeedLocalFood

Know more about us in our website: <https://www.agrobridges.eu/>

Add your website!

Agrobridges homepage - agroBRIDGES

agrobridges.eu • 1 min read

👁️ Did you know that the products coming from #ShortFoodSupplyChain business models are characterised by full or partial organic farming methods?

🌱 Products sold in local food systems are produced in an environmentally sustainable way, using less of inputs such as pesticides, synthetic fertilisers, animal feed, water and energy.

🏠 Among other benefits, you have direct contact with the producer, reducing the number of intermediaries, improving cohesion in urban areas, enjoying local products with higher quality standards, healthy eating, more environmentally friendly production methods, a lower carbon footprint, and a fairer price for producers and consumers.

👉 For this and more... #WeNeedLocalFood

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Below are some examples of social media publications on Instagram!

🧠🧠 Did you know that you can interact with local producers by using the hashtag #WeNeedLocalFood so that we can learn your real-time needs and you can learn more about the benefits of our business based on #ShortFoodSupplyChains?

📱 We invite you to interact with us and be part of our community

📝 Know some of the reasons why #WeNeedLocalFood:

- 🍎 We need high quality products
- 🤝 We need to reconnect producers and consumers
- 🌱 We need fresh and seasonal products
- ♻️ We need environmentally sustainable products

📌 These are just a few examples why #WeNeedLocalFood!

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VISUAL RESOURCES FOR SOCIAL MEDIA

- High-quality multimedia content will boost the reach and the impact of your publications.
- It is important that you only use images that are “free for use”. Websites will always provide you multimedia content of any copyright preference.
- The following websites will provide you with attractive content for your social media accounts.

shutterstock

pixabay

- Access to million of images.
- Affordable Plans.
- Powerful Search Features.
- It includes the commercial rights of the images.

- Free Service.
- Basic search feature.
- Free commercial license. Free for use
- Include video, photos and vectorial images.

- Access to million of images.
- Affordable Plans.
- Powerful Search Features.
- It includes the commercial rights of the images.

VISUAL RESOURCES FOR SOCIAL MEDIA

- Consider the images below for use in your social media accounts. You will be able to download them by clicking on the image.
- The following images are free of copyright restrictions and have been pulled from [PIXABAY](#).

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RELATED ACCOUNTS

You can get some inspiration by viewing some **Short Food Supply Chain** related accounts.

It is highly recommended to notice the different styles being used according the social media channel regarding:

- **Creativities**
- **Tone**
- **Text**
- **Branding**

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RELATED ACCOUNTS

ENTITY	WEBSITE	LINKEDIN	TWITTER	OTHER
COCOREADO	https://cocoreado.eu/	https://www.linkedin.com/company/cocoreado/	https://twitter.com/cocoreado	https://www.facebook.com/Cocoreado/
CIRCULAR BIOECONOMY CLUSTER	https://cbcsw.ie/	https://www.linkedin.com/company/circular-bioeconomy-cluster-south-west/	https://twitter.com/CBC_SW	-
BETA TECH CENTER	https://betatechcenter.com/	https://www.linkedin.com/company/betac/	https://twitter.com/BETA_TechCenter	-
BIOREFINERY GLAS	https://biorefineryglas.eu/	https://www.linkedin.com/company/biorefineryglas/	https://twitter.com/BiorefineryGlas	https://www.facebook.com/biorefineryglas/
GO-GRASS	https://www.go-grass.eu/	https://www.linkedin.com/company/go-grass/	https://twitter.com/GoGrassEU	https://www.instagram.com/gograsseu/
I2connectEU	https://i2connect-h2020.eu/	https://www.linkedin.com/in/i2connect-eu-a44607198/	https://twitter.com/i2connect_EU	https://www.facebook.com/i2connect.EU
COACH	https://coachproject.eu/	-	https://twitter.com/COACH_EUProject	-
EUFIC	https://www.eufic.org/en/	https://www.linkedin.com/company/european-food-information-council-eufic/	https://twitter.com/EUFIC	https://www.instagram.com/eufic/
CO-FRESH	https://co-fresh.eu/	-	https://twitter.com/COFRESH_H2020	-
RUBIZMO	https://rubizmo.eu/	https://www.linkedin.com/company/rubizmo/	https://twitter.com/rubizmo	-

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RELATED ACCOUNTS

ENTITY	WEBSITE	LINKEDIN	TWITTER	OTHER
BIO-BASED INDUSTRIES JOINT UNDERTAKING	bbi-europe.eu	https://www.linkedin.com/company/bio-based-industries-joint-undertaking/	https://twitter.com/BBI2020	-
BE-RURAL	https://be-rural.eu/	https://www.linkedin.com/company/beruralproject/	https://twitter.com/BE_Rural	https://www.instagram.com/BE_Rural/
BIOVOICES	https://www.biovoices.eu/#	https://www.linkedin.com/company/biovoices/	https://twitter.com/biovoices	https://www.instagram.com/biovoices/
ALLTHINGS.BIO	https://www.allthings.bio/	https://www.linkedin.com/company/allthingsbio/	https://twitter.com/AllThings_Bio	https://www.facebook.com/AllThingsBio/
BIOPEN	https://www.biopen-project.eu/	-	https://twitter.com/BIOPEN_Project	-
BIOSWITCH	https://bioswitch.eu/	https://www.linkedin.com/company/42308198/admin/	https://twitter.com/BIOSWITCH_eu	https://www.instagram.com/bioswitch.eu/
THE EUROPEAN BIOECONOMY NETWORK	https://eubionet.eu/	www.linkedin.com/groups/8793586	https://twitter.com/EuBioNet1	-
PLOUTOS H2020	https://ploutos-h2020.eu/	https://www.linkedin.com/showcase/ploutos-h2020/	https://twitter.com/ploutos_h2020	https://www.facebook.com/ploutos_h2020
SMARTCHAIN	https://www.smartchain-h2020.eu/	https://www.linkedin.com/company/smartchain-h2020-project/about/	https://twitter.com/Smartchain_EU	
POLIRURAL	https://polirural.eu/	-	https://twitter.com/PoliRural_H2020	https://www.facebook.com/PoliRural/?view_public_for=324962711741470

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7. <https://www.fao.org/family-farming/detail/en/c/427183/>
8. https://friendsoftheearth.eu/wp-content/uploads/2018/04/short_food_supply_chain_fact_sheet.pdf
9. European Commission, You are part of the food chain - Key facts and figure on the food supply chain in the European Union, in EU Agricultural markets briefs. 2015, European Commission: Brussels.
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